

International Seminar on Bio- Data and AI (ISBA) White Book 2023

DECLARATION

The primary content of this book is generated through artificial intelligence semantic recognition based on the reports of the ISBA speakers and has been published after review by the speakers. The views expressed in the text do not necessarily represent the main opinions of the speakers and the editors and are provided solely for the reader's learning and reference.

China National GeneBank
Database

ISBA official website

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White Book

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Biodata and AI technologies are hot research areas in the field of science and technology today, bringing unprecedented opportunities and challenges to fields such as healthcare, wellness, and environmental protection. To further promote the development of these areas, the successful organization of the International Seminar on BioData and AI (ISBA) has provided a platform for rich exchanges of ideas and insights among different groups of experts.

At the ISBA seminar, experts discussed the intersection of data science, life sciences, artificial intelligence, and society, with a special focus on the emerging policy and ethical challenges brought about by these rapidly developing fields. They collectively examined the progress China has made in scientific data management and sharing, emphasizing the necessity to further optimize data utilization and the importance of developing comprehensive national strategies to improve data standardization, privacy, and security.

Furthermore, the seminar delved into the role of artificial intelligence in biodata sharing and its revolutionary potential in fields such as precision oncology, public health, and genomics research. It also highlighted the opportunities and challenges in the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, including Guangdong, Hong Kong, and Macao. With its strong infrastructure, robust research capabilities, and dynamic economic environment, the region is poised to become a center for the development of biodata and AI. However, significant challenges must be overcome, including issues of data privacy and security, the need for effective data management and sharing mechanisms, and the ethical implications of AI applications.

In summary, the ISBA seminar served as a timely platform to discuss the exciting opportunities and pressing challenges in the field of biodata and artificial intelligence. It underscored the leading potential of the Greater Bay Area in this domain and emphasized the importance of addressing policy and ethical issues to ensure responsible and beneficial outcomes for society. The insights gained from this seminar will provide a reference for future strategies and initiatives in the field of biodata and AI in the Greater Bay Area and beyond.

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Greater Bay Area Declaration on Responsible Governance for Biodata and AI

2023.09.09

CODATA International Data Policy Committee
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China National GeneBank

Introduction

Following the 'International Seminar of Biodata and AI' held at the China National GeneBank (CNGB) in Shenzhen, China, on 9 September 2023, the undersigned institutions declare their intention to cooperate throughout the Greater Bay Area and internationally to develop policy for institutional standards and practices promoting our commitment to the responsible, legal, and ethical use of biodata and artificial intelligence (AI) for the benefit of the health and welfare of our societies and humanity at large. Our deliberations, informed by scientific expertise and ethical considerations, have culminated in this declaration to guide the responsible development, deployment, and use of biodata, data science, and AI applications for the benefit of humanity and the preservation of our natural world.

We recognize the transformative potential and the profound implications of these technologies as well as the potential of the life sciences (through the responsible use of biodata, data science, and AI) to revolutionize research into improving human health, preserving and (as appropriate) restoring

biodiversity, and contributing to a healthier planet for the inhabitation of persons, communities, and all living organisms. At the same time, we are mindful of the security, societal, and environmental risks associated with these technologies as well as their potential contributions to scientific knowledge and the improvement of the quality of life on the planet.

Preamble

Biodata, data science, and AI technologies have the capacity to revolutionize scientific research, conservation efforts, healthcare, and other domains of vital importance to the achievement of the UN Strategic Development Goals and a more humane planet with less suffering. However, their widespread adoption also brings forth significant ethical, social, and environmental challenges. We acknowledge the imperative of ensuring that the application of these technologies aligns with the principles of sustainability, equity, and respect for the inherent value of all life forms.

Principles

This Declaration affirms the fundamental values and principles for these sciences and technologies established in the UNESCO, Recommendation on Open Science (2021) and Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2022). The signatories here further recognize the richness in the diversity of societies, communities, and individuals globally, understanding that the implementation of these values and principles will vary according to the specific contexts of regional, national, and community standards and practices that determine what is of value to various cultural and political systems.

The undersigned commit to the following principles:

- 1. We will use biodata, data science, and AI within our institutions and in any cooperative engagements in a responsible, lawful, and ethical manner.**
- 2. We will respect the privacy of individuals, groups, communities, and societies.**
- 3. We will avoid bias and discrimination in our research and its applications; and we will invest in our science and research data and AI such as to reduce any existing biases.**
- 4. We will work to ensure that the benefits of biodata, data science, and AI are shared equitably across regions, nations, and communities.**
- 5. We will promote the designing AI systems for biodata and the life sciences that augment human capabilities and promote human**

dignity, while mitigating risks of harm, bias and deception.

6. We will commit to making algorithmic processes transparent, explainable and accountable to stakeholders.

7. We will promote Open Science, engaging in open and transparent research and development.

8. We will promote public understanding of biodata, data science, and AI with regard to their potential benefits as well as creating awareness of their potential risks.

9. We will engage with policymakers in the development of responsible legislation and regulation for promoting and safeguarding the public good through the responsible conduct of research on biodata in the life sciences, including with applications of AI.

10. We will regularly review and reassess our practices to ensure alignment with evolving

We believe that these principles are essential to ensure that AI and data science are used for the benefit all of humanity, for the promotion of biodiversity conservation, and the support of a healthy planet.

Actions

In order to support these principles, we further commit to the following actions:

1. To work cooperatively and with the larger scientific, ethics, and policy communities in the development of international standards for the responsible, lawful, and ethical use of biodata, data science, and AI in the life sciences, the medical sciences, and the environmental sciences.

2. To work cooperatively and with the larger scientific, ethics, and policy communities in the creation of mechanisms to ensure that these standards are implemented and enforced.

3. To work cooperatively and with the larger scientific, ethics, and policy communities in the promotion of funding for research on the ethical, legal, and societal implications of AI and data science.

4. To work cooperatively and with the larger scientific, ethics, and policy communities in the education of the public regarding the potential benefits and risks of the usages of biodata, data science, and AI.

5. To work cooperatively and with the larger scientific, ethics, and policy communities in order to foster a culture of responsibility within our institutions and networks while providing education on the lawful and ethical practices in the responsible handling of biodata and the applications of AI.

These actions will support our commitment and promote the use of biodata, data

science, and AI for the benefit of humanity, the protection of our natural resources, and the conservation of biodiversity and the preservation of a healthy planet.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we recognize the immense potential of biodata, data science, and AI to positively impact society and the environment while also acknowledging the need for security, vigilance, lawful conduct, ethical reflection, collaboration, and responsible governance. By adhering to these principles and taking collective action, we can harness the power of these technologies to build a more equitable, sustainable, and biodiverse world for the benefit of humanity.

Together we urge all stakeholders in the life sciences to join us in upholding these principles and promoting these actions.

The potential risks of using Generate AI models trained on Genetic data

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Genetic data involves Human Genetic Resources information requires great attention. International scientific research cooperation, external provision or open access of Human Genetic Resources to foreign parties require approval from regulatory authorities. Genetic data could also potentially be personal data. So, it's also be subject to the oversight of the National Cyberspace Office's administration. In addition, with the national regulation of generative AI, we should pay attention to the situation that there are multiple jointly regulated departments.

The era of Generative AI has arrived. It has significantly transformed various sectors, particularly the knowledge intensive ones. It will have a significant impact on knowledge intensive industries such as professional services, finance, healthcare, the internet, and high tech. The impact on labor intensive industries such as agriculture and construction is relatively small. Generative AI is expected to bring a cost reduction of 1.6% of the total operating costs in various industries in China, with an amount of 3.7 trillion yuan, through efficiency improvement. Baidu's 'ERNIE Bot' was one of the first large models to meet regulations under the new rules for Generative AI. Baidu's Biocomputing Large Model has proven effective in the medical and bioinformatics sectors. In the past decade, Baidu has invested over 140 billion yuan in research and development. In the field of biological computing, Baidu have demonstrated

outstanding performance in simulating and solving biological problems, such as protein folding and gene sequencing. The data training of the large model in multiple scenarios is interlinked, so ERNIE Bot can also support scientific research on genes.

The new rule in China shows a solid step forward for boosting the progress of generative AI. In fact, there's a big difference between the draft and the final version of regulation. Four key updates of the new rule for Generative AI services are as follows.

(1) If the state has other regulations on the use of generative artificial intelligence services for activities such as news publishing, film and television production, and literary and artistic creation, such regulations shall prevail. If industry

organizations, enterprises, educational and research institutions, public cultural institutions, relevant professional institutions, etc. develop and apply generative artificial intelligence technology and fail to provide generative artificial intelligence services to the domestic public, the provisions of these Measures shall not apply.

(2) The most noticed filing clause, which largely adopted our suggestions, now specifies that only AI with 'public opinion attributes or social mobilization capabilities' need to be registered.

(3) Real name registration is only required for those fulfilling instant messaging or information release.

(4) Training data is no longer required to be strictly true and accurate. If pre-training data includes personal information, personal consent is required.

The dual supervision of genetic data and Generative AI is a complex task that requires a deep understanding of both domains. AI is being used in various ways to enhance research and development in the life sciences, including protein design, molecular generation, Chat Bot, AI doctor and so on. We should pay more attention to gene analysis with AI services. In one hand, generative AI is strictly regulated in china. In the other hand, it is essential to be aware of essay consideration, data privacy and so on. Generative artificial intelligence with public opinion attributes or social mobilization capabilities requires strict filing systems. Illegal use of AI without security assessment poses a significant risk. Based on the country's sovereignty over genetic resources, the outflow of genetic data is strictly approved in China. Overseas organization collecting data, or international collaborations are pretty strict controls in china.

AI ethics and governance: translating principles into practice

Jeff Jianfeng Cao

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In order for us to translate all the principles of ethical guidelines, to achieve "value-aligned" AI, we need to follow an ethics by design approach in the responsible AI systems. How can we design and implement all the internal mechanisms to protect user and social interests in the AI development? How can we achieve the ethics by design in the AI systems? It will not only be that you have a better ethical AI culture in your company, or you have other, some kind of organizational structures, and also you need to take care of your business practices in the providing and marketing of the AI systems.

The construction of AI ethics can be divided into three stages. Principles began to be put forward in 2016, and then international consensus began to be sought in 2018. Since 2019, the principles have been gradually transformed into practice.

There is no doubt that managing AI has ethical risks, and ethicists should be included in AI development teams. AI technology and its applications are accelerating, laws and regulations are lagging behind. Major tech companies are embracing AI ethics research, and establishing AI ethics team.

Industry players are developing new solutions to solve the transparency issues of AI systems. Widely accepted is AI model cards / AI fact

sheet which is a proposed framework for better understanding how AI performs. Last year, Tencent Research Institute have published an explainable AI report that summarize some of their best practices. So, around all the many of the AI issues, industry is developing best practices to build more responsible AI development. This is a very important work that is still undergoing.

To put AI ethics principles into practice, exploring technical tools/solutions and ethics as a service (EaaS) are good solutions. There are many criteria to assess whether AI is trustworthy, such as reliability and robustness, transparency and interpretability, privacy and data protection, fairness, safety and security, responsibility, and so on. To solve issues such as expandability, fairness, privacy, safety, etc., and build trustworthy AI, technical tools are also necessary and important. To build trustworthy AI systems, major

tech companies are building technical solutions for ethical problems, even providing services to its customers in cloud & algorithm platforms. AI ethics startups are emerging, providing ethical tools and services to AI companies.

Besides the technical approach, regulation and the internal risk management, ethical standards and certification is also important. The industry and the government are trying to establish standards and certification to promote trustworthy AI systems. There are appropriate and other international standard setting organizations, together with other stakeholders developed ethical standards for AI systems. Many of the standard setting organizations have developed the trustworthy AI standards and many AI products have been got the trustworthy AI certification from the third-party body of this standard setting organization.

"Tech for Good" is initiative first launched by Tencent Research Institute. The positive focus is how can we use AI for the good of the society, and the negative focus is how can we mitigate the risks and build good human products and AI applications. Currently "Tech for Good" has more social consensus and has become a prevailing culture in China's tech industry, so people realize that technology means not only capability, but also responsibility.

To better govern AI system and build more ethical and responsible AI system, we will need multi-level governance regime to build trust in AI system. First, laws and regulations, industry self-regulations, education and awareness raising are very important and need lots of work to do. Another approach is focus on the market. AI ethics market will provide all of the professional market-based solutions to help build the trustworthy AI systems.

And the third one is the technical approach. AI alignment and other safety measures help build the safety and trustworthiness of the AI system to safeguard against misuse and bad use of the other potential by the users to abuse the AI system.

In conclusion, technology is a capability, and "Tech for Good" is a choice.

The impact of AI on open science - a publisher's perspective

Niki Scaplehorn

Springer Nature

Open Science provides a broader range of resources and collaborative opportunities for scientific research. Data Sharing is one of the important practices of Open Science. The rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) based on big data technology are novel innovations in open science and will exponentially increase the demand for open science. The publisher from Internationally renowned publishing agency Springer Nature describes the responsibility of publishing institutions in this new situation. Funding agencies are rapidly strengthening their data sharing policies to mandate data sharing at the point of publication. The publisher also highlights several areas that AI offers strong opportunities for making advances in Open Science:

1. AI will change the way researchers analyse and visualize their data. It's already possible for large language models (LLMs) to analysis data, generate and test hypotheses, and write up their findings.
2. LLMs will increase demand for open data.
3. AI will unlock our research archives and help to make sense of the research of the past.
4. AI will make it easier to be FAIR when you publish. The publisher also discussed about AI make it easier to create fake science.

But increasing sharing of data will help reduce the ability of these fake acts. In summary, open data sharing has become a major trend in promoting scientific research and innovation. Publishing institutions have a responsibility to guide and help scientific researchers share data under the new data policies.

Open Science can make all stages of scientific research more accessible, transparent, reproducible and reliable. This includes, for example, data acquisition, analysis, sharing, and publication. Researchers access other people's datasets, pursue replication studies and re-analyses, optimize statistical approaches to improve evidence assessment and engage in interdisciplinary collaboration, greatly promoting the development of scientific knowledge and the generation of innovation. Data sharing is one of the important practices of Open Science. Researchers create the data, spend money on creating data. But so much of the data becomes locked away, hidden and not reused. This is a huge waste of resources. By sharing data where it's possible, not just data, it also corresponds to code and protocols. These two things really go together, the protocol is effectively how data can be created and absolutely vital to data reuse. From the point of view of a publisher, it's very important because it provides a level of transparency and reproducibility as well. Clearly there are bad acts that would want to generate false data and fake science, it's much easier for publishers to prevent this from happening by forcing people to share their data a little bit more proactively. Increasing sharing of data will help reduce the ability of these fake acts.

The other thing that's sort of really making this the time for open science is movement on the policy front. Funding agencies are rapidly strengthening their data sharing policies, with a recent wave of top funders supporting full data sharing mandates. For example, recently the office for science and technology in the U. S. released a mandate for all US government funded research: not just open

access of the points of publication, but all of the underlying data should also be made public. For all publicly funded research in the US, which is a quite major development. Other funding agencies have been making similar sorts of mandates, really upgrading what were previously a recommendation to a mandate. Clearly not all data can be shared, with privacy often a concern for clinical data. But this is really a positive step in the right direction, and the similar sort of moves are being made in China as well, the importance of sharing is really being recognized. Centrally that creates an opportunity for us as publishers to support authors, and a level of responsibility. As publishers we can help funders to make sure that these mandates are actually fulfilled. Though it's quite complicated, there are different levels of raw data, now all of journals from Springer Nature have data availability statements where we ask authors to share how the data can be accessed. And, if not, why it can't be accessed, this is a certainly a step forward in the right direction. The publishers are going to have to be doing a lot more in terms of making sure that the raw data is there. Unfortunately, at the moment, researchers lack a level of training and guidance and actually funding as well to really share their data properly, and this is really something that needs to be addressed partly by funders and also partly by publishers through training programs.

With the rapid development of artificial intelligence technology, the potential for AI to transform the world of open science and really start to make progress in helping scientists to share and analysis their data more effectively and frequently. The researchers should already be aware of that open science is just becoming increasingly important. and AI is one of the reasons for this.

AI itself is really going to provide a much bigger impetus in the very near future towards open data. It's already possible for large language models to analyze data, generate and test hypotheses, and write up their findings, which will be going to create a huge demand for open data. It's more important than ever that science is machine-readable. AI 'scientists' with access to a properly annotated collection of the world's research data would be able to identify connections between results that go beyond individual research papers.

AI will change the way researchers do science in future. A special study covered in Nature released that a AI lab was able to generate a paper directly from a dataset. Researchers fed the large language model the data related to Different factors in the US population about health and diabetes status and asked AI to generate an interesting research question, and do the analyses to answer that question, and do all of the statistical work necessary and write the paper at the same time. This is really going to change the way we do science in future.

AI will change the way researchers analyse and visualise their data. LLMs allow anyone to create reproducible data analyses without writing code. 'Code interpreter' plugins for LLMs allow natural language interrogation of complex datasets, generating reproducible code to analyse the data and visualise the results.

AI will unlock the research of the past. Making sense of scientific articles. Scientific articles are designed for humans to read, but are terrible containers for scientific knowledge: Data are summarised into figures and tables: Protocols are summarized into Methods; Data become separated from the Protocols and Code that were

used to generate them; Information is locked in multi-panel images within PDF files; Options to share raw data and code are confusing and limited (Supplementary Data, Extended Data, references, hyperlinks). AI techniques can discover previously unknown associations and extract hidden information. AI will make it possible for machines to make sense of the research of the past, informing the AI scientists of the future.

AI will make it easier to be FAIR when you publish. Open science only works if the research is findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. This requires the creation of detailed, structured metadata for scientific datasets, which is difficult and time consuming. For many data types, metadata standards are not widely agreed. By 'understanding' scientific articles, LLMs will make it possible to automatically extract rich metadata, helping researchers to make their data fully FAIR as they deposit during publication. AI could also create full data/code/protocol publications based on the metadata.

Finally, AI will also make it easier to create fake science. Publishers face a technological arms race in detecting 'paper mills'. "Paper mills are profit oriented, unofficial and potentially illegal organizations that produce and sell fraudulent manuscripts that seem to resemble genuine research." [COPE]. Paper mills articles can already to be difficult for publishers to spot. Generative AI will make it easier than ever to write these papers and evade detection. Detecting use of generative AI cannot be the solution as there are appropriate uses of the technology to aid writing. Banning people from using AI to write their papers is very shortsighted. There've been already published

research highlights which initially drafted by AI at Nature. Open Science is an important part of the solution - by making full sharing of raw data the norm. Web3 (blockchain) technologies may also help to maintain trust in data sharing.

In summary, open data sharing has become a major trend in promoting scientific research and innovation, and research funding institutions have begun to support full data sharing mandates. Publishing institutions have an opportunity to guide and help scientific researchers share data in the new data policies. Big data provides fuel for the development of artificial intelligence, while the rapid development of artificial intelligence generates new value for big data, deepens the application of big data, and boosts more demands for open data sharing. Artificial intelligence will also bring new changes to the way scientists conduct research, help

scientists share data more efficiently and frequently, and create new possibilities for the future of open science.

AI Risk: A Systems Perspective

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The widespread application of large-scale AI has undeniably brought about unprecedented convenience. However, it is essential to recognize that AI also presents a range of risks and challenges that must be addressed. To date, several countries have made progress in establishing principles and governance mechanisms for responsible AI. For instance, Australia has principles that encompass human and societal impact, human-centered values, reliability and safety, transparency and explainability, fairness, privacy, protection and security, contestability, and accountability. It is imperative to prioritize research on responsible AI, examining it from diverse perspectives and emphasizing the advancements made by various countries in implementing principles and governance mechanisms for responsible AI.

Systems thinking approaches, such as systems modelling (Guan et al., 2022), systems engineering (Devaney, 2016), and cybernetics (Morasso, 2023) offer valuable insights for managing AI risks. Guan et al. (2022) propose a system dynamics-based risk-factor model for ethical risks in AI decision-making, while Hohma et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of system characteristics such as

balance, transparency, governance, and long-term orientation. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in the US provides a taxonomy of characteristics to consider when dealing with AI risks (Golpayegani et al., 2022).

While these principles have been established as generic guidelines based on learning from other domains, there is a lack of studies applying these principles to actual AI development. In practice, managing AI risks from a systems thinking perspective involves a comprehensive approach, starting from problem formulation to a lifecycle approach, understanding and identifying interactions, hyper-stakeholder management, including participatory modelling, and anticipatory thinking.

In this study, we consider the risks and challenges associated with AI by examining four compelling case studies that the author had carried out in the past. These case studies shed light on the potential pitfalls and complexities that arise in the realm of AI, allowing us to gain a deeper understanding of the risks involved.

The first case involves the development of an AI

Issues/ Cases	AI 4 Chem Plant	Fraud/ Compliance Detection	Aged Care Risk	Socio-Political Systems Model (Digital Twin for Political Instability)
Problem Formulation	Collaborative and participatory approach to formulate the problem, maintained throughout lifecycle + Key stakeholder touch points also.			
	Engineers, Plant Operators	Compliance, Insurance, End Users	Nursing, Research, Compliance, End Users	Defence Analysts, Academic Experts in Political Science, Psychology, Sociology
Data Management & Governance	Plant Data. Sensitive commercial data. Attempt for clean data by sampling multiple sources.	Transactional, Census Data with commercial sensitivity and privacy	Transactional & Health Data. Sensitive client health data	Data: Country DBs incl. WVS, Macro, Population, Political Climate, Expert Survey, Unstructured News, Open Data
	Significant Ad-Hoc Cleansing. Imputation for small % of numerical data. Upstream Data Cleansing recommended. Fusion of Disparate Data. Quality improved, but FAIR was not considered. Project Data Governance was put in place.			+ Differential Diagnosis for developing "validable" Human Behaviour models
Modelling	Range of Techniques: XGB, LR, DL... Time Series -> CS Bespoke XAI, Imbalanced Classes Corrected for Classification.			Mechanism based Whitebox Sim Model Cognitive AI Agent centric, supported Systems Dynamics, Simple Agents.
	Deployed 30+ AI models across the plants after significant consultations & using MLOps. Human-in-the-LOOP & Decision Making considerations (HILDMC).	Deployed a AI models + dashboard app after significant consultations, HILDMC	Proof of Concept (PoC) accepted. Augmenting PoC to deploy. HILDMC.	Deployed 10+ AI models, with interacti dashboards' intervention explorers, across a number of Gov Agencies (US). HILDMC
Risk Management & Lifecycle Approach	Considers inter-linked lifecycles, interdependencies and failure points for risk management, including general Risk, Ethics, Explainability, Trust			Multi-level validation to augment trust: External Validity (Systems & Agent), ph Conceptual, Process, Narrative Validity
	Transition and Adoption (REETTA). Deploys checklists for best practices to control risks.			

Table 1: Comparison across the Cases

system for chemical process monitoring in various chemical plants. The system detects deviations in processes and provides advance warnings. The system has achieved an accuracy of around 88% in most cases, with a small percentage of cases having lower accuracy. The development and deployment of this system have been challenging.

In the second case, AI is used for insurance fraud detection. The system identifies non-compliance and provides recommendations, including nudging individuals towards regulatory actions. It analyzes data to identify anomalies and predict non-compliant behavior, providing risk scores and explanations for its recommendations. Currently, the system is only capable of initiating specific processes, such as communication and nudging, for low-risk cases.

The third case focuses on predicting the risk in elderly care. The AI system predicts the risk of harm for elderly individuals living alone or independently and provides recommendations to prevent harm. The performance of the model is satisfactory, but there are still privacy and security concerns that

need to be addressed in subsequent iterations.

The fourth case involves a simulation model for predicting and exploring social and political conflicts. This model serves as a training system and provides broad recommendations for further research. It creates a virtual world where agents interact and make decisions based on socioeconomic and political conditions, shaping the trajectory of the virtual world.

The cases presented in Table 1 demonstrate the extensive range of applications for artificial intelligence (AI) and underscore the significance of collaboration with stakeholders during the development process. The acquisition and management of data are critical components of these AI systems, and it is essential to address concerns regarding data quality and privacy. It is emphasized that data correction and analysis are more important than the algorithmic aspect, highlighting the need for accurate and reliable data for AI models. To improve the quality of the data, measures such as data cleansing and

AI 4 Chem Plant	Fraud/ Compliance Detection	Aged Care Risk	Socio-Political Systems Model (Digital Twin for Political Instability)
Data Confidentiality Security & Privacy Protection	Data Bias: Ensuring a diverse dataset was critical.	Confidentiality and Protection of Sensitive Data could lead to Data Bias: Solution: Ensuring a diverse dataset was critical.	Representation Bias: Using unrepresentative data led to a risk of predictions being skewed. Ensuring a diverse dataset or utilizing techniques like data augmentation and re-sampling.
Quality and Bias: Process changes tracked and data validation Audit of the data.	Privacy Concerns: Data anonymization and encryption techniques	Privacy Concerns: Data anonymization and encryption techniques	Confirmation Bias: Implementing differential Diagnosis, blind or double-blind methods during data sourcing and evaluation, as well as inviting third-party reviews, helped reduce confirmation bias.
Mis-Classification/ Prediction: Validation, Human Oversight	Misclassification Risks: Used as Assistive Tool. Human-in-the-loop:	Misclassification Risks: Used as Assistive Tool. Threshold Tuning: Optimal thresholds were determined to balance false positives and negatives.	Ethical Dilemmas: Using the model to intervene or take actions in regions. Model scope is for understanding. Setting clear use-case guidelines and collaborating with international bodies.
Job Loss: Augmentation tool	Integrating human oversight.	Over-reliance on Technology: Training sessions to use the AI tool as an aid,	
Accountability: Cleared up.	Over-reliance on Technology: Training sessions to use the AI tool as an aid,	Transparency and Explainability: Black-box algorithms raised trust issues. Used explainable AI techniques	Misinterpretation and Over-reliance: Emphasizing that the tool should be used in conjunction with human expertise and ground-level data was vital.
Data Drift: Adaptive Learning, regular updates. Continuous monitoring	Transparency and Explainability: Black-box algorithms raised trust issues. Used explainable AI techniques	Ethical Dilemmas: Who gets to decide what's "risky"? Ethical committees and their collective decisions	Feedback Loops: Continuously updating the model and recalibrating
	Feedback and Improvement: Risk model might become outdated. A feedback mechanism and model updated	Feedback and Improvement: Risk model might become outdated. A feedback mechanism and model updated	

Table 2: Risks and Ethics in Different Contexts

preprocessing are necessary. The deployment of AI models involves human involvement and decision-making, indicating that these systems are not intended to replace human judgment but rather to assist and support decision-making processes. Human expertise is required to interpret the results and make informed decisions based on the AI recommendations. Managing risks is a crucial consideration in the AI systems lifecycle, including addressing concerns related to data privacy, bias, and potential ethical implications. To protect data privacy, measures such as anonymization and encryption techniques can be employed, and ensuring a diverse dataset can help mitigate bias in AI models.

Drilling down a little deeper, one can also look at the key issues in AI Risk. As one can see, data sensitivity is common for all cases, but is most important for Fraud Detection and Aged Care cases, owing to sensitive nature of the data handled. In the case of Chemical Plant case, it takes the form of business confidentiality. In all cases, however, appropriate security, privacy and data protection policies need to be implemented. However, in the case of Aged Care, this takes an interesting relationship with bias. For example, data privacy issues might compel minority aged care clients to decline data sharing. While protecting the individual's privacy, this decision would decrease the number of data points available for model

training in the case of minority groups, resulting in a biased model.

In summary, the effective management of AI risk through a systems thinking approach requires the establishment of a comprehensive governance process (Felländer et al. 2022) prior to any activity, the dedication of sufficient resources towards problem formulation, the engagement and collaboration of all relevant stakeholders, the identification and modeling of potential risk factors, the adoption of proactive anticipatory thinking, consideration for deployment at the onset, and the integration of responsible AI principles.

It is particularly important to consider the responsible AI principle, which involves providing explanations to enhance trust

and adoption, understanding the cyclic nature of subsystems, interactions and dependencies, paths to value, and points of risk and failure. The iterative nature of the development process is an advantage in this regard. Additionally, effective collaboration, data management, human oversight, and risk mitigation are critical factors in the AI systems lifecycle and are fundamental to the successful application of AI technologies across diverse domains.

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Semantics of genomics and AI

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Artificial intelligence has emerged as a powerful platform to streamline the processing and analysis of complex genomic datasets, enabling researchers to identify and explore patterns that govern the genetic basis of important diseases or phenotypes. There are challenges in standardizing ontological conventions and formats in genomics and metabolomics, which limit the application of artificial intelligence. We are a research team investigating plant transient and trans-generational memory in plants, and our recent findings revealed a role for prions-like proteins in the cross-talk between plant stress and memory. We integrate multiple data types to reduce data dimensionality and correlate stress with memory pathways. Additionally, our team has developed semantic tools that utilize artificial intelligence to automate knowledge extraction from literature, facilitating a more effective understanding of specific research domains.

Lack of sufficient depth of regional data has led to challenges in generating large-scale biomedical genomics datasets for the Indian population, but these challenges are easier to overcome in agri-biology and soil genomics. The role of governments in creating new opportunities to generate country-specific datasets and data-sharing methodologies is crucial. Studying the complete DNA composition of organisms is a massive and complex task. Besides making sense of the meaning and importance of genetic information, we need to understand the function, structure, and regulation of genes and other genomic elements. Faced with vast and intricate genomic data, researchers often encounter significant challenges. Artificial intelligence is emerging as a powerful methodology in addressing

these challenges by streamlining the processing and analysis of large-scale multi-omics datasets, identifying relevant patterns, and assisting scientists in finding gene mutations associated with diseases and predicting disease risks. However, one has to appreciate the importance of structured data availability for AI to work. For example, one of the most successful examples of AI in biology has been the 'AlphaFold', a breakthrough that was only possible because all the globally published data on protein 3-D structure has been openly available in standardized form (the PDB format). Artificial intelligence holds vast prospects for personalized medicine and genomics, but this will depend on availability and processing of large datasets in globally standardized repositories like

the RCSB and GenBank that provide researchers with abundant resources. New Large Language models (LLMs) using GPT or BERT-technology are transforming the ability of AI to explore the "dark matter" of protein and DNA sequence space for instance, via ProtGPT and codonBERT, but it remains to be seen how widely the research community may accept and use these models, as has been done for the AlphaFold. In genomics and metabolomics, there is a lack of interdisciplinary standardized data naming conventions and formats, which may limit the application of artificial intelligence in these fields. Environmental scientists aspire to utilize machine intelligence and develop new transformers to investigate biodiversity. We have high expectations for upcoming research that can help us understand the integration of the atmosphere, biosphere, geosphere, and

cryosphere and apply AI to comprehend the Earth and model climate change better. With ecologists at the Ambedkar University of Delhi and Forest Depts in various National Parks of India, we are exploring human wildlife conflict, particularly across the biodiversity hotspots in the country. While AI and genomics have revolutionized our understanding of biology, there is tremendous untapped potential in predicting climate change using biodiversity data and the world is yet to fully realize this goal. Here we describe our efforts and goals in using AI and genomics to address questions in botany and biodiversity. Over the past few years, plant learning and cognition has emerged as one of the most fascinating fields of study, especially in view of the intricate mechanisms evolved by plants to survive under ever-changing unfavourable and adverse

environmental conditions. For plants, memory related research has been limited to physiological perspectives for 'Touch-Me-Not' and some other species, but there are several unanswered questions about whether memorized experiences are genetically fixed and heritable or remain epigenetically variable. We recently found evidence for proteins with prion-like features as mediators of stress memory in plants, connecting for the first time, the lesser-known protein-based signals, with the better-known epigenetic signals in plant stress acclimation. Our team took a novel AI based perspective, unlike the conventional 'mechanical' approaches, to understand complex plant traits, leading to the identification of links that would not have otherwise been discernible. We discovered widespread occurrence of PrLPs across the green lineage, from algae to flowering plants, with a significant enrichment of transposons and retro-transposons in the rice prionome. We then conducted a systems-wide analysis to integrate the rice interactome, transcriptome, and regulome to decipher how each gene influences others in an intricate pattern of networks, that revealed PrLPs as hubs connecting plant transient and trans-generational memory for the first time. In summary, this work has consolidated a rapidly growing field, paving the way for the scientific community to (re-)evaluate the significance and meaning of concepts like memory and learning for a plant. The work involved the development of new algorithms not just in AI for genomics, but also for molecular geo-tagging of nodes in a graph theoretical framework, that enabled better visualisation of spatiotemporal complex data systems with application in genomics, conservation ecology and invasion biology. The machine intelligence based workflow was established in 2019, and is freely available for any researcher to apply to their own area of

research.

To address the challenge in accessing literature, a bottleneck for most life science researchers, we have co-founded semanticClimate.org. Under this citizen science movement, we have devised AI based teaching innovations through Colab and jupyter notebooks, apart from research innovations implementing AI for deep learning plant chemistry towards deciphering the Earth Metaphenome. The development of a student authored prototype python toolkit "#semanticClimate" using AI over Natural Language Processing (NLP) has helped us in the path to democratise knowledge and in creation of global knowledge champions, whereby over 3000 rural /urban Indian students acquired AI and data science skills during pandemic via our online teaching interventions and #semanticClimate internships. The barrier to entry is zero in these capacity building efforts, enabling every researcher to harness artificial intelligence for knowledge extraction. This tool has the potential to revolutionize how we gather and utilize knowledge, allowing one to gain a more effective understanding of research in specific domains. Our team is based in Cambridge and India, currently working to enhance these tools and providing multilingual capabilities.

Rectifying Bias in A.I. Training Data

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As A.I. has become more prevalent in our everyday lives, we have started to see the limitations of the technology. Even though we believed computers were immune to human emotions and bias, computers today still fall back on data collected and created by humans, which is riddled with bias and trends that will affect how the A.I. acts going forward. World Data Systems has partnered with ENRICH Local Contexts to promote and standardize Traditional Knowledge (TK) Labels. The TK labels are a collection of machine-readable pieces of metadata that are designed to reclaim Indigenous Peoples's traditional knowledge, cultural expressions, and heritage from where they had been misrepresented, misappropriated, or used without authorization. We strive to advocate for the global adoption of the TK labels not only to safeguard Indigenous cultural protocols and rights associated with digital content but also to provide a more accurate record of human history, statistics, and data. By incorporating TK labels, we give A.I. and people a much easier time finding information about Indigenous peoples and can help provide a more accurate representation for research that uses big data. So, we will lay out the basics of how TK labels work and provide a demonstration of how to use the Local Context hub to apply them to research and repositories.

Digital infrastructures are not neutral and can carry biases from other systemic frameworks. When it comes to A.I. processing information, there are two main types of biases at play. The first is cognitive bias, which refers to unconscious errors in thinking that influence judgments and decisions. These biases can arise from people's natural tendency to group things and process information. A.I. designers and algorithms can unconsciously introduce around 180 different human biases identified by psychologists. The specific concern

is the lack of complete data, which can lead to non-representative results if not considered within the appropriate context. In the healthcare field, discriminatory practices and systemic issues can result in flawed data, which in turn affects algorithms and produces biased outcomes. This disproportionately affects minority and vulnerable groups, including indigenous peoples and their cultures, which have often been misrepresented and mixed up in popular culture and academia.

To address these biases and misrepresentations, Traditional Knowledge (TK) labels offer a solution. While not legally binding, TK labels create a safe space for traditional manifestations of intellectual property and their associated concepts, which existing copyright laws often fail to capture and regulate. These labels introduce a new type of machine-readable metadata that can be applied to research data, making it accessible to cultures worldwide. They are designed to be customizable by indigenous communities to suit their specific needs and are divided into three broad categories aligned with different aspects of indigenous cultural heritage: Provenance Labels, protocol Labels, and Permission Labels.

In summary, while TK Labels provide a solution to reclaim Indigenous knowledge and promote accurate representation, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the biases present

in digital infrastructures and A.I. processing. By doing so, we can strive for a more inclusive and equitable use of technology and data.

Provenance and protocol labels are important for recognizing and preserving indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage. Provenance labels indicate the origin of data, while protocol labels outline traditional regulations for its use. These labels help distinguish genuine information from misinformation and ensure indigenous communities have control over their knowledge. By attaching these labels, indigenous communities can make their information stand out to A.I. systems and algorithms. This creates visibility and acknowledges their contributions. Biocultural labels are used in biodiversity and genetic research to recognize indigenous rights over traditional knowledge and land. While only indigenous communities can apply these labels, research institutions and others

can refer to them to respect and acknowledge indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage.

In collections, indigenous communities can register their projects or collections in the local capex and apply these labels. This registration and application process notifies indigenous communities of potential rights and interest in their publications, data, or holdings. They can then decide which labels to attach to their projects and collaborate with others who are open to working together. For specific labels like biocultural or traditional knowledge labels, there are notices available. The attribution and completion of these labels indicate that there is already some information present, such as indigenous artifacts or other attached labels, but more details or additions are needed.

The Genome database from Simon Fraser University are collaborating using an open platform to facilitate communication and collaboration. Users can access notices by creating an account on the website. This allows them to access their files and project and link their accounts to other institutions or researchers. The local context website also provides a direct line of communication with indigenous communities to apply labels to notices and facilitate transparent communication and knowledge sharing. The labels have been tested with indigenous communities in Australia, New Zealand, and other countries, and case studies are being opened up with Canadian indigenous groups.

Currently, the labels do not fit comfortably within existing standards, but efforts are being made to adjust the standards to include the necessary framework to represent indigenous rights and interests. Traditional knowledge labels help A.I. algorithms find genuine and digitized knowledge,

providing a more comprehensive understanding of population dynamics, history, and cultural impact.

AI-based Radiology- Histology-Genomic Co-profiling for Precision Oncology

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The fusion of multimodal data such as medical imaging, pathological images, and genomic sequencing data has become a new breakthrough in the research field of precision oncology. Artificial intelligence provides a powerful tool for multimodal data fusion. However, how to integrate multimodal cross-scale radiology, pathology, and genomics data remains an unresolved challenging issue. Solving this problem relies on in-depth research in interdisciplinary fields, including artificial intelligence, clinical medicine, and oncology, with the goal of benefiting patients with brain tumors by providing more accurate diagnoses and more effective treatments. By integrating medical imaging, pathological images, and genetic data, the characteristics of tumors can be characterized more accurately and comprehensively, thereby guiding the next generation of precision diagnosis and treatment for cancer.

In recent years, artificial intelligence has demonstrated tremendous clinical value in assisting the diagnosis and treatment of cancer through medical imaging. Recently, the latest treatment guidelines for many common cancers have undergone key adjustments: in addition to imaging and pathology, genetic markers have been incorporated as important bases for

diagnosis and treatment in these guidelines, signifying the official arrival of the era of molecular diagnosis and treatment of cancer. For many common cancers, to provide a treatment plan that conforms to the latest guidelines, it is essential to integrate imaging, pathology, and genetic data. This new clinical demand significantly drives the innovation of artificial intelligence in diagnostic

and therapeutic technologies. Traditional models derived from natural image recognition cannot be directly applied, and there is an urgent need to construct new artificial intelligence models for imaging-genetics..

Taking glioma, the most common malignant brain tumor in adults, as an example: Glioma is the most prevalent primary brain tumor in adults, and its diagnostic gold standard is the examination of post-surgical pathological slices. Pathologists observe the slices under a microscope and classify and diagnose based on histological morphological characteristics. With the release of the 5th edition of the World Health Organization (WHO) Central Nervous System Tumor Classification standards in 2021, the pathological diagnosis of gliomas has undergone revolutionary changes. According to the latest guidelines, the type and grade of gliomas can only be definitively determined by combining histological features with molecular markers, emphasizing the crucial role of molecular information in integrated diagnosis. Consequently, as clinical needs represented by the WHO guidelines evolve, artificial intelligence diagnostic and therapeutic algorithms also need to adjust accordingly, shifting from single-modal to multimodal data inputs, including imaging, pathological images, and genetic sequencing. This presents new theoretical and methodological challenges, such as how to quantitatively describe the macroscopic imaging-microscopic gene correlations and how to construct diagnostic and therapeutic models by integrating imaging-genetic heterogeneity data. On the other hand, artificial intelligence technologies, represented by deep learning, are considered a 'black box'. Therefore, current research needs to contemplate how to provide new biomedical

interpretability for black-box artificial intelligence from multimodal data and how to integrate biomedical prior knowledge more effectively. Multimodal fusion requires re-understanding tumors from multiple scales, including imaging, pathology, and genetics, to achieve more precise tumor characterization and typing, guiding the precise diagnosis and treatment of tumors.

To address these new challenges, breakthrough research in tumor intelligent diagnosis and treatment has moved beyond the existing framework of medical imaging intelligence. The focus is now on the cutting-edge research of new intelligent models for image-pathology-genetics fusion. In the realm of imaging-genetics correlation analysis, hypotheses regarding the correlation between imaging features, molecular pathways, and driver genes have been proposed and validated, building a bridge between macroscopic imaging and microscopic genes. This addresses the foundational theoretical and key evidential gaps in imaging-genes research, filling an important niche in the quantification of 'image-gene mapping relationships' in this frontier field. In integrated diagnosis of gliomas, a novel artificial intelligence-based integrated diagnostic system for gliomas has been developed. This AI diagnostic system takes digital pathology images as input and directly outputs integrated diagnostic results that comply with the 5th edition of the WHO guidelines, achieving accuracy comparable to human pathologists. In the immunotherapy of gliomas, imaging-genetics fusion intelligent models are used to identify immune microenvironment subtypes, further improving the accuracy and efficacy of tumor immunotherapy. In the precise subtyping of gliomas, the current WHO integrated subtyping remains imperfect, with inconsistencies

between subtypes and prognostic and biological characteristics. Further research into modifications such as protein phosphorylation helps explain the heterogeneity of gliomas. Integrating proteomics data is crucial for multi-scale fusion analysis of imaging, pathology, and genetics, and for the discovery of new subtypes.

To achieve this goal, we draw on the unified modeling concepts of holism and reductionism, incorporating multi-scale data such as millimeter-level imaging features, micrometer-level pathological morphology, and molecular-level genomic, transcriptomic, and proteomic sequencing into artificial intelligence modeling. We aim to develop new methods for multi-scale fusion learning to comprehensively analyze

tumors from macro to micro levels. The goal is to achieve multimodal cross-scale data fusion in gliomas and realize precise tumor subtyping and prognostic prediction to potentially extend the overall survival of patients. This work also faces many challenges, the most central of which is how to describe the biological correlations between multimodal cross-scale data. Are these correlations the result of biological factors, or are they merely coincidental statistical illusions? How can we validate these complex correlations through experiments? How can these correlations be used to construct accurate and efficient artificial intelligence models? We still need to conduct more in-depth research to address these questions.

Progress and challenges of scientific data in China

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In recent years, a series of important measures in China have pushed the national scientific data work to new heights. This report focuses on the momentum of scientific data-driven innovation and development, the progress of scientific data work in China, and the challenges faced in scientific data work. It shares the progress and related reflections on scientific data work in China.

The Momentum of Scientific Data-Driven Innovation and Development

In recent years, a series of important measures in China have pushed the national scientific data work to new heights. In 2019, China first proposed the theory of data elements and subsequently carried out a series of explorations and released some important documents. Currently, China has established nearly 60 data trading institutions. The “Opinions on Building a Data Foundation System to Better Play the Role of Data Elements” in 2022 innovatively clarified the framework of the data property rights system with “three rights separation”. The establishment of the National Data Bureau in 2023 marks the entry of national-level digital transformation into the era of data-driven. Under this significant era background, scientific data has also been given a new mission.

Another important issue is that the ChatGPT technology and applications in this year have brought revolutionary impact to us. At the same

time, it has also brought a new challenge, which is how data can adapt to the needs of new technologies. Large-scale models have shown tremendous effectiveness in various fields, and their development is closely related to the support of high-quality standardized data. Apart from text corpora, other types of data seem to be unprepared, which is a problem that needs to be addressed. However, compared to large-scale models in the general domain, large-scale models in the research field are relatively lagging behind, which may be related to the responsiveness of scientific data itself. Therefore, we need to consider how scientific data can support the work and innovative development of large-scale models, open science, and future needs.

In summary, we are currently facing important issues such as the development of data element theory, the challenge of data adapting to new technologies, the application of large models, and the integration of open science. These issues

require our attention and efforts to promote the development of scientific data work.

The Progress of Scientific Data Work in China

The history of scientific data work in China can be traced back to 1978 when the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) initiated the scientific database project. Since then, research institutions represented by CAS have been continuously promoting the development of scientific data work in China. In 2000, the Ministry of Science and

Technology of the People's Republic of China organized a group of experts to compile a research report on the construction of national basic science and technology databases, outlining the future development blueprint for scientific data in China. According to this report, China started to lay out the national scientific data initiatives from 2002, including pilot projects, initiation, and improvement of services, ultimately leading to the establishment of the National Data Center in 2019. In addition, various provinces and cities have also issued their own implementation rules for scientific data management, promoting local data work. This year, Guangdong Province released a draft of detailed regulations that clearly define and plan the scientific data management model, data center system, and scientific data centers. Furthermore, institutions such as the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, the Ministry of Transport of the People's Republic of China, and the Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China have also issued relevant documents. Overall, China has made significant progress in

scientific data work over the past few decades, including the data work carried out by provinces and cities.

China has also made remarkable progress in scientific data management. In terms of the total amount of data resources, by the end of 2020, the total capacity of the 20 national data centers in China exceeded 100 petabytes. In terms of data intellectual property rights, data resources generated with government budget funds have social public attributes, which can be understood as jointly owned by the state and the public. Data publication is a practical way to address the rights and interests of data contributors. In terms of infrastructure, China's scientific and technological infrastructure is relatively well-developed and capable of participating in international cooperation. The Science Data Bank has achieved breakthrough results and can provide data storage services for experts from over 70 countries worldwide. In terms of standards, TC486 has published more than 20 standards related to scientific data. In addition, China has participated in the publication of Catalogue of Life Checklist Bank and the Chinese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library, which have global influence. These achievements reflect some of the progress China has made in the field of scientific data management.

Challenges in Scientific Data Work in China

1. The openness and management of sensitive information: Both domestically and internationally,

there is an increasing demand for strengthened management and security of sensitive information in open operations.

2. Definition of data intellectual property rights: The definition of intellectual property rights for scientific data requires careful consideration and redefinition in light of the new concept of separating the three rights.

3. Challenges in data quality: The perception of scientific data quality needs to be reexamined, and the assurance of data quality should be integrated into the capacity building and lifecycle processes of data production or management institutions.

4. Data security and ethical issues: Seeking a balance between openness and security, it is necessary to prioritize data ethics as a prerequisite to ensure the organic integration and implementation of data ethics, artificial intelligence ethics, and other related aspects.

5. International cooperation and contribution: How to make greater contributions internationally, especially in the field of large models and open science initiatives, is an important issue.

In the era of big data, the development of scientific data in China has presented a new situation. We should seize the trends and opportunities in the development of scientific data, and make comprehensive efforts in various aspects such as cultural construction, full lifecycle management of scientific data, development models of scientific data management institutions, exploration of data governance mechanisms, breakthroughs in key data technologies, and the construction of

research application ecosystems. This will push the work of national scientific data to a higher level of innovation.

Technological Innovation and Climate Governance: A Comparative Perspective on China, the US, and Europe

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Global climate change has emerged as one of the most pressing challenges confronting the world. Despite the concerted efforts by nations worldwide to pursue measures aimed at managing carbon emissions and realizing climate targets, there exist conspicuous disparities between developed and developing countries on issues of climate diplomacy, collaboration, and policy response. While China, the US, the EU, and smaller countries all strive to attain carbon neutrality, they adopt differing specific strategies that represent divergent institutional models. Achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement entails enhancing the level of investment in clean energy. China, for instance, is committed to promoting carbon neutrality through investments in green and new energy industries. However, the EU is optimistic that carbon emissions can be regulated through the deployment of market forces, which comprises strategies such as carbon pricing and establishment of carbon emission trading systems. In comparison, the US intends to leverage the "Inflation Reduction Act" as its primary legislative tool to allocate nearly \$400 billion over the next decade towards a significant cut in carbon emissions. Notably, many low- and middle-income

countries face a considerable climate financing deficit that limits their capacity to tackle the climate crisis, while some developed nations have failed to fulfill their financial pledges to assist smaller countries. Variations such as these not only manifest in the differing trajectories towards attaining carbon neutrality but also have an impact on international climate diplomacy and response strategies, including the enforcement of financial commitments to smaller states, the rise of trade protectionism, limited tax exemptions to domestic enterprises in the US, and the EU's carbon border adjustment policy, which concentrates on levying tariffs on products sourced from regions with lenient carbon emission restrictions. Overall, these distinctions exacerbate the challenges of strengthening worldwide collaboration in tackling climate change.

Artificial intelligence as an emerging data mining and analysis tool offers potential for more efficient and innovative solutions to address climate change, thereby creating new opportunities for climate governance. Turning AI into a strategic asset to mitigate the effects of climate change requires the implementation of leadership strategies through national policies and plans. By integrating AI with

climate change, a coordinated synergy between environmental protection and innovation can be achieved that drives green transformation and fosters sustainable development in the climate field. The development and adoption of AI technology to tackle climate change should not be treated as an isolated action but rather as a global public enterprise and a unified global initiative that mandates a broad collaboration between developed and developing countries. Only through a collective effort can effective and innovative technological solutions be developed and implemented to accelerate the process of climate governance while achieving the sustainable development goals of the planet. However, the innovation of AI technologies may incur substantial energy costs and potentially generate environmental consequences. In particular, training neural networks and processing vast amounts of data require a significant quantity of computational resources, while transporting and storing data in cloud computing also draws a considerable amount of energy, leading to a resultant increase in carbon emissions. Additionally, because of geopolitical factors, applying high-performance, low-power chips, and AI technologies to climate governance presents challenges for many countries. These are issues that require careful consideration within the context of technological innovation for climate governance in China, the US, and Europe.

Co-building trustworthy open-science infrastructures for AI governance: Discussion based on introduction to the Global Open Science Cloud Initiative

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Background

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021) highlights several key pillars in which open science infrastructures are on the list. Open science infrastructures refer to research facilities that support open science physically or virtually. To break silos across domains and regions for better data flow, research e-infrastructures are shifting to open-science design and development to support science and technology research.

Introduction to the Global Open Science Cloud Initiative

In line with United Nation's Open Science movement, the Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) Initiative was launched in 2021, adopted by ISC CODATA as an important task in the Decadal Programme 'Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges.' GOSC is supported by seed funding from the Chinese Academy of Science (CAS). Meanwhile, CODATA and the Computer

Network Information Center (CNIC), CAS, jointly work to promote international alignment. The GOSC Initiative aims to co-design and co-build a global Open Science environment where trusted research e-infrastructures are better interconnected and interoperable, enabling worldwide cutting-edge science exploration. Moreover, this initiative endeavors to facilitate accessibility,

interconnectivity, interoperability, and inclusiveness of worldwide research e-infrastructures to support international research collaborations for Open Science.

Compromised by the Steering Groups, four Working Groups together with the first six selected Case Studies, currently, the GOSC initiative is co-built by over 200 worldwide experts (GOSC IPO, 2023), namely stakeholders ranging from policymakers, funding agency representatives, technological developers, research e-infrastructure representatives, domain experts, and others. To guarantee the accessibility of research resources, the interconnectivity of research facilities, interoperability between humans and machines, and inclusiveness for all, this GOSC initiative highlights several actions to co-build trustworthy research ecosystems.

Firstly, stakeholders are invited to co-design interoperable and robust policies for running open science clouds. Discussions include Rules of Participation for open-science service delivery, "Data Characteristics Affecting Levels of Openness" as open metrics, and implementing guidelines for OSCs alignment, especially the legal and economic factors addressing the effective governance of OSCs. The light-weight demonstrations are in progress, including crisis data essentials discovery, responsible open science case studies, and others. Moreover, technical exploration features a peer-to-peer GOSC generic technical framework design and enhanced GOSC toolkits for technical interoperability. The GOSC technical framework comprises enhanced internet connectivity, cloud federation for computing and data storage, open data fabric, integrated open software, and open community for global research collaboration (Chen et al., 2023;

Chen et al., 2021). Under the FAIR governance rules and policies, alliances of security, trusts, and sustainability are also established. Among all of them, the CSTCloud AAI (Authorization and Authentication Infrastructure, <https://aai.cstcloud.net/>) has been established to support federated authentication, virtual organization, and authorization management as well as others to ensure resources flow and service delivery in a secured and trustworthy manner (Zheng & Liu, 2023). Supported by the federated AAI, a GOSC testbed prototype (Li, 2022) is in progress to validate service interoperability. Based on integrated resources of IaaS layers and driven by thematic and disciplinary open communities, this GOSC testbed will be co-developed inclusively by GOSC members to provide services to developers, data scientists, disciplinary experts, and others.

Shifts to better governance of cutting-edge technologies

We see the potential opportunities that cutting-edge technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and others, may bring. Open science infrastructures highlight interoperability and interconnectivity among facilities, naturally providing soil for large-scale ICT deployment. It may provide flexible and robust solutions governing technologies and efficient deployment disciplinarily. However, there are still several steps for the future GOSC to ensure robust support for effective AI governance in the long run. For GOSC policy design and development (CODATA, 2021), a better understanding of levels of boundaries for open science, open data, and open research e-infrastructures is vitally important, together with the co-building of a trustworthy ecosystem inclusive to all GOSC potential stakeholders.

Besides, technologies will go further on secured AAI construction (Zheng & Liu, 2023) and peer-to-peer development of the GOSC testbed (Li, 2022) to support effective ways of running a growing scale of AI models. Shared facilities will surely demonstrate the efficacy and effectiveness of AI governance under an open-science way of design and development.

Moreover, we would extend our warmest welcome to you for more engagement in the GOSC community, such as to co-design and co-develop the GOSC testbed, to join the Working Groups for in-depth engagement to fulfill the GOSC objectives, to join the GOSC policy dialogue for open-science-infrastructure strategies or to propose new case studies for GOSC demonstrations. We see the potential open science infrastructures may bring in pursuing the Sustained Development Goals by the United Nations, which will, in turn, provide a pragmatic way for the sustained governance of AI as well as other cutting-edge ICT developments in the future.

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